

Intravenous Dexmedetomidine vs Propofol for intraoperative moderate sedation during spinal anesthesia

Aravind M.*¹, Balasubramanian S², Aishwarya S.³, Ralleen Jacob E.⁴

*1. Post Graduate, Department of Anesthesiology, Trichy SRM Medical College Hospital and
Research Centre*

*2. Professor, Department of Anesthesiology, Trichy SRM Medical College Hospital and Research
Centre*

*3. Associate Professor, Department of Anesthesiology, Trichy SRM Medical College Hospital and
Research Centre*

4. Assistant Professor, Panimalar Medical College Hospital and Research Center

**Corresponding Author : Aravind M*

Abstract

Background: In our study, we compare sedative properties of Dexmedetomidine (alpha 2 agonist) and Propofol (GABA potentiator) using OAA/S (Observer's Assessment of Alertness/ Sedation) and find which is better for sedation during surgery to relieve anxiety. Dexmedetomidine and Propofol are commonly used drugs for sedation.

Methods: This prospective observational study was conducted in the department of anesthesia at Trichy Medical College Hospital and Research Centre, among 40 cases undergoing surgery under sub arachnoid Block. Patients aged 18-60 years from both genders and ASA class I and II were included in the study. SPSS was used to analyse the data.

Results: In this study patients of ASA class I and II undergoing surgery under sub arachnoid block with mean age of 40.3 years, height of 164.65 cm, weight of 63.48 kg, BMI of 23.44 and equal distribution across both genders. On observations, heart rate was lower ($p < 0.001$) with group receiving Dexmedetomidine; mean arterial pressure (MAP), Dexmedetomidine group had higher MAP ($p < 0.001$) and on OAA/S score, Dexmedetomidine group had better sedation scores ($p < 0.05$) compared to Propofol.

Conclusion: Patients undergoing surgery are anxious and to alleviate this, sedation during the procedure gives better patient comfort. Of the two drugs, Dexmedetomidine provides better sedation and stable parameters than Propofol.

Key Words: Dexmedetomidine, Propofol, Intra Op Sedation, OAA/S

Introduction

Regional anaesthesia, including spinal, epidural, or peripheral neural blockade, has been proposed as a primary anaesthetic technique to mitigate the risk of perioperative complications by avoiding intubation and mechanical ventilation^{1,2}.

Cardiovascular and respiratory stability, rapid postoperative recovery, and the preservation of protective airway reflexes are the benchmarks for spinal anaesthesia. From the patient's perspective, staying awake, early family contact, and early food intake are the cornerstones of their self-assurance and postoperative recovery^{3,4}.

Despite the growing prevalence of spinal anaesthesia in anaesthetic practice, anxiety, discomfort, and a lack of sedation control remain significant patient concerns. To address this issue, adjunctive medications are employed to reduce anxiety, alleviate discomfort, enhance haemodynamic stability, and induce a sense of tranquilly during spinal anaesthesia⁵. Moderate sedation is the term used to describe the drug-induced state of conscious depression in which patients purposefully respond to verbal commands, either alone or with mild tactile stimulation⁶.

Moderate sedation has been achieved through the use of a variety of agents. Propofol's rapid recovery and simple titratability render it advantageous for sedation. In addition to extending the duration of spinal anaesthesia, intravenous (i.v.) dexmedetomidine also provides effective sedation with negligible side effects⁷.

There is a scarcity of research that compares the efficacy of intravenous dexmedetomidine and propofol for moderate sedation during spinal anaesthesia, including their sedative properties, haemodynamic effects, and adverse effects. Hence the study.

Objectives

- To compare the intravenous Dexmedetomidine and Propofol for moderate sedation in patients undergoing surgery under spinal anesthesia

Methodology

The study design was a Prospective Cohort study conducted in department of Anaesthesiology at SRM Medical College, Trichy, a district tertiary care facility. Participants were enrolled from May 2024 to July 2024 after the Institutional Medical Ethics Committee granted approval. The study recruited patients between the ages of 18 and 60, regardless of gender, and from American Society of Anaesthetists class I and II. The study did not enrol patients who were taking alpha 2 adrenergic receptor antagonists, calcium channel blockers, or angiotensin converting enzyme inhibitors, as well as those with history of dysrhythmias, anaphylactic reactions, seizures, or are pregnant or lactating. There was also no recruitment of patients in the overweight BMI category.

Simple random sampling was done and from the previous studies, sample size was fixed at 40, divided into two groups (Dexmedetomidine and Propofol groups) of 20 patients each. Informed written consent was obtained. Computer-generated random numbers were employed to designate patients to one of two groups. Group D (dexmedetomidine) was administered an initial dosage of 1 µg/kg over a 10-minute period, followed by a maintenance dose of 0.5 µg/kg every hour. A maintenance dose of 2.5 mg/kg/hour was administered to the propofol group (Group P) after an initial dose of 6 mg/kg/h was administered over a 10-minute period. The anaesthesia procedure was standardised for all patients. Patients were not administered any premedication. Patients were encouraged to divulge any pain or discomfort they encountered during the operation. The modified observer's assessment of alertness/anaesthesia scale (OAA/S) was employed to evaluate the degree of preoperative sedation.

In the operating room, patients were connected to a multipara (Minday uMEC 12 monitor) to monitor non-invasive blood pressure, pulse oximeter, and electrocardiograms. Measurements were taken at the baseline. 18G cannula was secured for intravenous access. Crystalloids were administered to all patients as per Holiday Segar formula. Using a Arrow BD 25G Quincke type spinal needle, a lumbar puncture was conducted at the L3-L4 interspace under aseptic conditions. Required dosage of 0.5% Bupivacaine heavy was administered into the subarachnoid area after the unrestricted flow of CSF was achieved. Patients were subsequently subjected to a supine position. The study medications were administered according to the group allocation and evaluated for the extent of sensory blockade.

The duration required to achieve an OAA/S score of 4, which is indicative of moderate sedation conditions, was used to define sedation onset⁸. The sedation score of 3 was achieved by administering propofol and dexmedetomidine at a consistent rate throughout the procedure. Sedation levels were assessed at 5-minute intervals. Ten minutes prior to the conclusion of the procedure, the infusion was discontinued. From baseline measurements until the conclusion of the procedure, the following parameters were recorded at 5-minute intervals: ECG, heart rate (HR), systolic and diastolic blood pressure, mean blood pressure (MBP), respiratory rate (RR), oxygen saturation (SpO₂).

Effective analgesia (the time between spinal administration and the first request for supplementary analgesics) and recovery time (the time required to return to a sedation score of 4 or higher on the modified OAA/S scale after the study drug infusion was discontinued) were documented in all patients.

Data Collection and measurement tools

Observer's Assessment of Alertness/Sedation (OAA/S) scale: a tool used to assess the level of sedation in patients, particularly during procedures that require moderate or deep sedation. It measures a patient's response to verbal stimuli and is used to ensure that the sedation level is appropriate for the procedure.

Results:

The data (baseline attributes, HR, MABP, OAA/S scale, side effects incidence) of the groups were tabulated in MS excel. Statistical analysis was done by SPSS software (trial version 28). The data was analysed by using descriptive and inferential statistics. Categorical variable such as gender and AHA were summarized as frequencies. Association of groups with gender and AHA was analysed using a Chi-squared test. Continuous variables such as age, height, weight, BMI, HR, MABP and OAA/S scale were checked for normality by Shapiro Wilk test and normal distribution of the data was observed and hence they were summarized as mean \pm standard deviation. Inter-group comparison of continuous variables was done using Independent t-test. Statically significance was fixed at $p < 0.05$

Table 1: Demographic profile of study participants of both the groups

Baseline attributes	Group-D (n=20)		Group-P (n=20)		p value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Age (years)	40.85	12.65	39.75	10.9	0.77
Gender (M;F)	10;10		10;10		1
Height (cm)	164.6	2.46	164.70	3.34	0.91
Weight (kg)	62.55	3.10	64.4	3.14	0.08
BMI (kg/m ²)	23.14	1.42	23.74	0.79	0.11
ASA-PS (I/II)	14;6		12;8		0.50

Data are expressed as mean \pm SD and comparison done using independent T test

*p value <0.05, significant

Table 1 represents the baseline characteristics such as mean of age, height, weight and BMI of the study participants in Group D and Group P and comparison between the two groups were done using Independent t-test ($p > 0.05$). The categorical variables such as gender and ASA PS were represented in frequencies and compared using chi-squared test ($p > 0.05$). This infers that the confounding variables are not statistically significant and hence doesn't influence the study parameters.

Figure 1a: Demographic profile of mean age (years), mean height(cm), mean weight(kg) and mean BMI(kg/m²)

Figure 1a represents the clustered bar diagram of the two study groups (D and P) for continuous variables like mean age, height, weight and BMI.

Figure 1b: Demographic profile- Gender

Figure 1c: Demographic profile- ASA-PS

Figure 1b and 1c represents the percentages of gender and ASA PS among the two groups (D and P).

Table 2: Mean Heart Rate(beats/min) over time

Time	Heart rate		p value
	Group D	Group P	
Baseline	78.85 ± 5.35	81.70 ± 3.6	0.06*
5 min	67.90 ± 5.95	82.05 ± 9.05	<0.001*
10 min	65.10 ± 6.49	79.15 ± 10.53	<0.001*
15 min	62.85 ± 7.71	80.10 ± 3.04	<0.001*
20 min	65.75 ± 5.67	77.25 ± 2.88	<0.001*
25 min	63.55 ± 7.39	77.75 ± 3.42	<0.001*
30 min	62.95 ± 8.71	76.55 ± 3.39	<0.001*
35 min	62.95 ± 8.83	77.40 ± 2.30	<0.001*
40 min	64.60 ± 8.07	78.65 ± 3.30	<0.001*
45 min	63.25 ± 6.63	73.55 ± 3.25	<0.001*
50 min	63.75 ± 6.21	72.50 ± 3.40	<0.001*
55 min	64.50 ± 5.28	76.15 ± 1.50	<0.001*
60 min	64.95 ± 5.28	76.75 ± 2.12	<0.001*

Data are expressed as mean ± SD and comparison done using independent T test
*p value <0.05, significant

Graph 2a: Mean Heart Rate (beats/minute) trends over time

The table and graph represents the mean ± SD of HR(bpm) among two groups (Group-D and Group-P) at various time points. At baseline, there were no significant differences. However, at subsequent time points (5 to 60 minutes), Group-D consistently exhibited significantly lower heart rates compared to Group-P (*p < 0.001). This trend suggests that Group-D had a lower heart rate post-baseline compared to the Group P.

Table 2: Mean Arterial Blood Pressure (mm Hg) over time

Time	MABP (mmHg)		p value
	Group D	Group P	
Baseline	77.65 ± 3.83	79.05 ± 3.12	0.35
5 min	76.10 ± 7.92	62.30 ± 7.06	<0.001*
10 min	78.05 ± 7.78	66.10 ± 7.62	<0.001*
15 min	77.60 ± 3.89	61.85 ± 3.41	<0.001*
20 min	76.55 ± 2.72	66.25 ± 3.77	<0.001*
25 min	77.65 ± 3.67	63.10 ± 4.00	<0.001*
30 min	76.85 ± 3.18	63.30 ± 4.07	<0.001*
35 min	75.70 ± 3.18	66.25 ± 3.75	<0.001*
40 min	74.35 ± 3.70	63.55 ± 4.08	<0.001*
45 min	80.75 ± 3.16	62.95 ± 4.27	<0.001*
50 min	77.00 ± 3.96	62.70 ± 4.91	<0.001*
55 min	76.75 ± 3.57	64.40 ± 3.99	<0.001*
60 min	78.15 ± 3.62	64.35 ± 3.42	<0.001*

Data are expressed as mean ± SD and comparison done using independent T test
 *p value <0.05, significant

Figure 2: Mean Arterial Blood Pressure (mm Hg) trends over time

The table 2 and figure 2 represent the mean ± SD of MABP (mmHg) among two groups (Group-D and Group-P) at various time intervals starting from baseline to 60 minutes. At baseline, there were no significant differences. However, from 5 to 60 minutes, Group-D consistently exhibited significantly higher MABP compared to Group-P (*p < 0.001). The line graph trend also suggests that Group-P had a markedly lower MABP post-baseline compared to the Group-D.

Table 3: Mean OAA/S Scale scores over time

Time	OAA/S Scale score		p value
	Group D	Group P	
Baseline	4.95 ± 0.22	4.90 ± 0.31	0.86
5 min	4.30 ± 0.47	3.60 ± 0.75	0.001*
10 min	3.95 ± 0.22	3.50 ± 0.61	0.01*
15 min	3.05 ± 0.51	3.45 ± 0.60	0.04*
20 min	3.00 ± 0.32	3.20 ± 0.70	0.05*
25 min	2.90 ± 0.31	3.40 ± 0.60	0.004*
30 min	2.85 ± 0.36	3.25 ± 0.64	0.04*
35 min	2.45 ± 0.51	3.30 ± 0.57	<0.001*
40 min	2.20 ± 0.41	3.40 ± 0.60	<0.001*
45 min	2.15 ± 0.37	3.55 ± 0.51	<0.001*
50 min	2.10 ± 0.31	3.55 ± 0.51	<0.001*
55 min	2.05 ± 0.22	3.65 ± 0.59	<0.001*
60 min	2.75 ± 0.55	3.55 ± 0.51	<0.001*

Data are expressed as mean ± SD and comparison done using independent T test
*p value <0.05, significant

Figure 3: Mean OAA/S Sedation score trends over time

The table 3 and figure 3 represent the mean ± SD of OAA/S Scale score among two groups (Group-D and Group-P) at various time intervals starting from baseline to 60 minutes. At baseline, there were no significant differences. However, from 5 to 60 minutes, Group-D consistently exhibited lower OAA/S Scale scores compared to Group-P (*p < 0.05). The line graph trend also suggests that Group-D had a markedly lower OAA/S Scale score post-baseline compared to the Group-P.

Discussion

Our investigation revealed a notable reduction in average heart rate (HR) induced by dexmedetomidine within 5 minutes of initiating the infusion. The observed difference remained consistent during the treatment and may be attributed to the sympatholytic characteristics and vagal mimetic effects of dexmedetomidine. Our study findings appear to be very consistent with those of Al-Mustafa, et al.⁹ and Mahmoud, et al.¹⁰

Meanwhile, the Mean arterial pressure (MBP) was markedly reduced in Propofol group, 5 minutes after initiating infusion and remained lower throughout the entire procedure compared to Dexmedetomidine group. The decrease in mean blood pressure (MBP) in patients under Propofol treatment may be ascribed to the direct and potent inhibitory impact of Propofol on sympathetic outflow, resulting in vasodilation. No significant difference in mean arterial blood pressure (MBP) from the baseline value was observed between Dexmedetomidine group throughout the whole length of the procedure. Given its ability to reduce sympathetic outflow and circulating catecholamine levels, dexmedetomidine is anticipated to result in a reduction in mean arterial blood pressure (MBP) comparable to propofol. Nevertheless, administration of higher dosages of dexmedetomidine directly affects the postsynaptic vascular smooth muscle, leading to vasoconstriction. It is plausible that the sympatho inhibitory effects of dexmedetomidine were somewhat counteracted by direct action via α -2 induced vasoconstriction. Corresponding findings to our investigation were reported by Arain et al.¹¹, Al-Mustafa et al.⁹, and Mahmoud et al.¹⁰

An earlier onset of sedation in the propofol group compared to the dexmedetomidine group is due to the high lipophilicity of propofol, which allows it to quickly penetrate the central nervous system. Arain, et al.¹¹ observed that propofol provided the desired drowsiness within 10 minutes, but had a duration of 25 minutes. administered with dexmedetomidine. Comparable findings were achieved by Abdelkareim, et al.¹²

Comparisons between Group D and Group P reveal a much higher degree of sedation throughout the treatment. The conclusions gained in our investigation are strongly corroborated by the findings of Arain et al.¹¹, Kaya et al.¹³, and Hoy and Keating.¹⁴

Both Group D and P had a notably longer mean recovery time. A possible reason for the shorter recovery period in Group P compared to Group D is the fast metabolism and elimination of Propofol. The result of our investigation establishes a strong correlation with the findings of earlier authors.^{11,15}

The Dexmedetomidine group showed a considerably longer mean duration of effective analgesia compared to the Propofol group. The outcome of our study is similar to the findings reported by other writers^{9,14}. Dexmedetomidine has analgesic effects by its interaction with adrenoreceptors located in the spinal cord. Jorm and Stamford noted that dexmedetomidine had an inhibitory impact on the A6 group of the locus coeruleus nerve, situated in the brain stem¹⁶. The extension of spinal analgesia following intravenous administration of dexmedetomidine may be attributed to its supraspinal effect.

The aforementioned elements, including improved sedation, consistent cardiorespiratory profile, and analgesic effect, led to notably higher degrees of overall patient satisfaction in the dexmedetomidine group. Results of our investigation are highly consistent with those of Arain, et al and shah, et al.^{11,17}

In conclusion, while our study provides valuable insights into the comparative effects of Dexmedetomidine and Propofol, several limitations must be considered. The relatively small sample size and single-centre design may limit the generalizability and robustness of the findings. To address these limitations, future research should aim to include larger and more diverse populations across multiple centres. Additionally, incorporating long-term follow-up and utilizing advanced methodologies will help in obtaining more comprehensive and generalizable results. By addressing these areas, future studies can further elucidate the relative benefits and risks of Dexmedetomidine and Propofol, ultimately contributing to improved clinical practice and patient outcomes

References

1. Beaupre LA, Jones CA, Saunders LD, Johnston DWC, Buckingham J, Majumdar SR. Best practices for elderly hip fracture patients. A systematic overview of the evidence. *J Gen Intern Med.* 2005 Nov;20(11):1019–25.
2. Rodgers A, Walker N, Schug S, McKee A, Kehlet H, van Zundert A, et al. Reduction of postoperative mortality and morbidity with epidural or spinal anaesthesia: results from overview of randomised trials. *BMJ.* 2000 Dec 16;321(7275):1493.
3. Asehnoune K, Albaladejo P, Smail N, Heriche C, Sitbon P, Gueneron JP, et al. Information et anesthésie : que souhaite le patient ?*1. *Annales Françaises d'Anesthésie et de Réanimation.* 2000 Oct 1;19(8):577–81.
4. Bhattarai B, Rahman TR, Sah BP, Singh SN. Central neural blocks: a quality assessment of anaesthesia in gynaecological surgeries. *Nepal Med Coll J.* 2005 Dec;7(2):93–6.
5. De Andrés J, Valía JC, Gil A, Bolinches R. Predictors of patient satisfaction with regional anesthesia. *Reg Anesth.* 1995;20(6):498–505.
6. Bahn EL, Holt KR. Procedural sedation and analgesia: a review and new concepts. *Emerg Med Clin North Am.* 2005 May;23(2):503–17.
7. Hayashi Y, Maze M. Alpha 2 adrenoceptor agonists and anaesthesia. *Br J Anaesth.* 1993 Jul;71(1):108–18.
8. Patki A, Shelgaonkar VC. A Comparison of Equisedative Infusions of Propofol and Midazolam for Conscious Sedation During Spinal Anesthesia - A Prospective Randomized Study. *J Anaesthesiol Clin Pharmacol.* 2011;27(1):47–53.
9. Al-Mustafa MM, Badran IZ, Abu-Ali HM, Al-Barazangi BA, Massad IM, Al-Ghanem SM. Intravenous dexmedetomidine prolongs bupivacaine spinal analgesia. *Middle East J Anaesthesiol.* 2009 Jun;20(2):225–31.
10. Mahmoud M, Gunter J, Donnelly LF, Wang Y, Nick TG, Sadhasivam S. A comparison of dexmedetomidine with propofol for magnetic resonance imaging sleep studies in children. *Anesth Analg.* 2009 Sep;109(3):745–53.
11. Arain SR, Ebert TJ. The efficacy, side effects, and recovery characteristics of dexmedetomidine versus propofol when used for intraoperative sedation. *Anesth Analg.* 2002 Aug;95(2):461–6, table of contents.
12. Aloweidi A, Al-Mustafa M, Alajlouni J, Mas'ad D, Hamdan M, AL-Ghanem S, et al. Intravenous Dexmedetomidine or Propofol Adjuvant to Spinal Anesthesia in Total Knee Replacement Surgery. *Jordan Medical Journal.* 2011 Jan 1;45:174–83.

13. Fn K, B Y, G T, A Y, A G, Eb M, et al. Intravenous dexmedetomidine, but not midazolam, prolongs bupivacaine spinal anesthesia. *Canadian journal of anaesthesia = Journal canadien d'anesthésie* [Internet]. 2010 Jan [cited 2024 Sep 4];57(1). Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/20039221/>
14. Hoy SM, Keating GM. Dexmedetomidine: a review of its use for sedation in mechanically ventilated patients in an intensive care setting and for procedural sedation. *Drugs*. 2011 Jul 30;71(11):1481–501.
15. Khurana P, Agarwal A, Verma R, Gupta P. Comparison of Midazolam and Propofol for BIS-Guided Sedation During Regional Anaesthesia. *Indian J Anaesth*. 2009 Dec;53(6):662–6.
16. Jorm CM, Stamford JA. Actions of the hypnotic anaesthetic, dexmedetomidine, on noradrenaline release and cell firing in rat locus coeruleus slices. *Br J Anaesth*. 1993 Sep;71(3):447–9.
17. Shah PJ, Dubey KP, Sahare KK, Agrawal A. Intravenous dexmedetomidine versus propofol for intraoperative moderate sedation during spinal anesthesia: A comparative study. *Journal of Anaesthesiology, Clinical Pharmacology*. 2016 Jun;32(2):245.